

**The Role of *Inter Se* Agreements in Neutralising the Sunset Clauses of
International Investment Agreements:
Approach of the European Union to the Energy Charter Treaty**

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Abstract:

Efforts to achieve net-zero targets have led to debates about the adequacy of international legal frameworks governing energy investment. Initially created to promote energy cooperation and investment protection, the Energy Charter Treaty is now seen as undermining climate goals. The European Union withdrew from the ECT after a failed modernisation process and legal challenges such as the *Achmea* and *Komstroy* decisions. To neutralise the treaty's 20-year sunset clause, the EU concluded an *inter se* agreement among its member states. This article examines the legal feasibility of that strategy under international law, particularly the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, and principles, notably acquired rights and legitimate expectations. The findings show that while the EU's strategy aims to advance climate goals, it raises concerns about legal certainty and investor rights.

Keywords: Sunset clause; *inter se* agreement; Energy Charter Treaty; investor–state arbitration; *Achmea*, *Komstroy*, Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties.

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1. Introduction

The world is undergoing an unprecedented energy transformation to combat the harmful effects of climate change.² Driven by urgent international climate commitments and bolstered by ambitious national policies, countries are rapidly expanding sustainable energy solutions. Recent data from the International Energy Agency (IEA) show that global renewable power capacity additions jumped by almost 50% in 2023, reaching nearly 510 gigawatts (GW) of new capacity – the fastest growth rate in two decades.³ Even more striking, the IEA projects that total renewable capacity will soar to about 7,300 GW by 2028.⁴ For perspective, that 2028 forecast is roughly 50% greater than the entire global power generation capacity of all fossil-fuel and nuclear plants combined as of 2021.⁵ Yet this remarkable growth is still not enough to meet the world’s climate targets.⁶ This shortfall underscores the critical need to reassess existing international frameworks governing energy investments, as misaligned policies could stymie progress toward global climate objectives.

One such framework under intense scrutiny is the Energy Charter Treaty (ECT).⁷ Over the past three decades, the ECT has become the world’s most frequently invoked investment treaty in the energy sector,⁸ with more than 160 investor–state arbitration cases filed under its provisions as of mid-2025.⁹ By protecting fossil-fuel assets via investor–state dispute settlement (ISDS), the ECT has been criticised as a serious obstacle to national policies aimed at phasing out coal, oil, and gas.¹⁰ As members of the European and National Parliaments of the EU member states have argued, the treaty’s investor protections effectively serve as a “life insurance” for fossil fuel projects, putting a brake on the EU’s climate ambitions.¹¹

² International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), ‘World Energy Transitions Outlook 2022’ (*IRENA*, 2022).

³ International Energy Agency (IEA), ‘Renewables 2023: Executive Summary’ (*IEA*, 2023).

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ IEA, ‘Renewables 2021: Executive Summary’ (*IEA*, 2021).

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ Energy Charter Treaty (adopted 17 December 1994, entered into force 16 April 1998) 2080 UNTS 95.

⁸ International Energy Charter, ‘The Energy Charter Treaty (ECT) Remains the Most Frequently Invoked IIA’ (*International Energy Charter*, 2019).

⁹ International Energy Charter, ‘Statistics’ (*International Energy Charter*, 2023).

¹⁰ See Kate Aronoff, ‘The Obscure Treaty That Could Kill a Global Green Recovery’ (*TNR*, 2022); Fabian Flues, Pia Eberhardt and Cecilia Olivet, ‘Busting the myths around the Energy Charter Treaty: A guide for concerned citizens, activists, journalists and policymakers’ (*PowerShift, Corporate Europe Observatory (CEO) and the Transnational Institute (TNI)*, 2020).

¹¹ Members of the European and National Parliaments, ‘Statement on the Modernisation of the Energy Charter Treaty’ (*Anna Cavazzini*, 3 November 2020).

In 2017, recognising these issues, the ECT’s contracting parties launched a modernisation process to update the treaty’s provisions.¹² Negotiations in subsequent years sought to address criticisms by, for instance, carving out fossil-fuel protections and affirming states’ right to regulate for climate mitigation.¹³ However, as this process was underway, a pivotal legal development fundamentally altered the landscape for the EU countries in the ECT. In March 2018, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) delivered its landmark *Achmea*¹⁴ judgment, holding that investor–state arbitration clauses in intra-EU bilateral investment treaties are incompatible with EU law.¹⁵ The CJEU found that allowing an investor from one EU state to sue another EU state in an arbitral tribunal outside the EU judicial system infringes on the autonomy of EU law.¹⁶ Although *Achmea* dealt with a bilateral treaty, it sent a clear signal that *intra-EU* investment arbitration is precluded by the EU Treaties.¹⁷ Building on that principle, the CJEU in September 2021 issued an even more consequential ruling in *Republic of Moldova v. Komstroy*.¹⁸ In *Komstroy*, the EU’s top court applied *Achmea*’s reasoning to the ECT, decisively insisting that the treaty’s investor–state arbitration clause “must be interpreted as not being applicable to disputes between a Member State and an investor of another Member State.”¹⁹

Despite the CJEU’s clear pronouncements in *Achmea* and *Komstroy*, arbitral tribunals have not uniformly yielded. Some international tribunals continued to accept jurisdiction over intra-EU ECT claims, reasoning that the ECT is an independent international agreement not subject to EU law constraints.²⁰ This divergence has created a legal quagmire: EU law deems intra-EU arbitration clauses invalid, but arbitral panels may uphold them, leading to conflicting outcomes.

¹² Energy Charter Secretariat, ‘Modernisation of the Energy Charter Treaty’ (*The Energy Charter*, November 2017).

¹³ Lukas Schaugg, ‘Why the Energy Charter Treaty Modernization Does not Deliver for Climate’ (*IISD*, December 2024).

¹⁴ Case C-284/16 *Slowakische Republik v Achmea BV* EU:C:2018:158.

¹⁵ *Ibid* [60].

¹⁶ Cristina Contartese and Mads Andenas, ‘EU autonomy and investor-state dispute settlement under *inter se* agreements between EU Member States: *Achmea*’ (2019) 56 *Common Mkt. L. Rev.* 157.

¹⁷ *Ibid*.

¹⁸ Case C-741/19 *République de Moldavie v Komstroy LLC* [2021] ECLI:EU:C:2021:655.

¹⁹ *Ibid* [66].

²⁰ See *Infracapital F1 Sàrl v Kingdom of Spain* (ICSID Case No ARB/16/18) Award (2023).

Meanwhile, the ECT modernisation talks struggled to deliver consensus. By mid-2022, negotiators had drafted a set of amendments.²¹ EU member states ultimately grew dissatisfied with the result, arguing that the changes did not go far enough to align the treaty with Paris Agreement²² goals or to resolve the intra-EU arbitration issue.²³ In May 2024, this process culminated in a formal decision: the Council of the EU approved the coordinated withdrawal of the EU and Euratom from the Energy Charter Treaty.²⁴

Withdrawal alone does not erase the ECT’s protections, because the treaty contains a 20-year sunset period that keeps investment guarantees alive for two decades after withdrawal.²⁵ In practical terms, even post-withdrawal climate measures could trigger ECT arbitration by investors for years to come. To address this, the European Commission and EU states have moved to neutralise the sunset clause among themselves. In late 2024, the EU initialled an *inter se* agreement (hereafter “agreement”) asserting that the ECT’s arbitration clause and sunset clause “do not apply and have never applied” in intra-EU relations.²⁶ This bold move aims to prevent an onslaught of ECT-based claims during the sunset period, which could otherwise saddle European governments with an estimated €1.3 trillion in liabilities by 2050 if fossil-fuel protections continued unabated.²⁷ In doing so, the EU seeks to safeguard its climate objectives and regulatory autonomy against legacy investor claims.

However, this development also raises significant legal questions, which this article will examine: Can a subset of treaty parties lawfully defang a multilateral treaty’s sunset clause among themselves? More generally, is the EU’s strategy to blunt the ECT’s climate-threatening provisions feasible under international law? To answer these questions, the analysis will first unpack the

²¹ Council of the European Union, ‘Agreement in Principle on the Modernisation of the Energy Charter Treaty’ (Annex to Energy Charter Secretariat Doc CC 750 Rev, 24 June 2022), contained in Council of the European Union, ‘Energy Charter Treaty Modernisation’ WK 9218/2022 INIT (27 June 2022).

²² Paris Agreement to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (adopted 12 December 2015, entered into force 4 November 2016) UNTS Reg No I-54113.

²³ Martin Dietrich Brauch, ‘The Agreement in Principle on ECT “Modernization”: A Botched Reform Attempt that Undermines Climate Action’ (*Columbia Center on Sustainable Investment*, 2022).

²⁴ The European Council, ‘Energy Charter Treaty: Council gives final green light to EU’s withdrawal’ (*The European Council*, 2024).

²⁵ ECT (n 7) Art. 47(3).

²⁶ European Commission, ‘Communication ... on an agreement ... on the interpretation of the Energy Charter Treaty’ COM (2022) 523 final, 5 October 2022, Annex ‘Subsequent Agreement on the Interpretation of the Energy Charter Treaty’

²⁷ Anna Cavazzini, ‘Statement on the modernisation of the Energy Charter Treaty’ (*Anna Cavazzini*, December 2020).

framework of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT)²⁸ regarding treaty interpretation and modification, and then assess how principles of international law might affect investors' rights in the wake of the EU's inter se agreement.

2. The Vienna Convention's Framework: Interpretation vs. Modification

The EU's agreement pursues an unusual dual strategy: it seeks both to interpret the ECT and to modify it for intra-EU purposes.²⁹ Under orthodox doctrine, interpretation merely elucidates the meaning a treaty provision has always had (thus operating *ex tunc*, with retrospective effect), whereas a modification or amendment changes the treaty's normative content for the future (*ex nunc*).³⁰ By asserting that the ECT's investor–state arbitration clause and sunset clause “do not apply and never applied” in intra-EU relations,³¹ the EU agreement tries to compress these two distinct operations into a single instrument. In essence, it strives to gain the benefits of an authentic interpretation without securing the unanimous consent that genuine multilateral interpretation would require,³² and simultaneously to achieve the effect of a treaty modification without a formal amendment adopted by all parties.

In view of this conflation, it is crucial to analytically disentangle “interpretation” from “modification” when assessing the agreement. The following sub-sections therefore examine how the VCLT's rules on treaty interpretation (Section 2.1) and on treaty modification (Section 2.2) apply to the EU's approach.

2.1 Interpretation Under VCLT Article 31

VCLT Article 31 sets out the general rule of treaty interpretation. Relevantly, Article 31(3) directs interpreters to take into account certain post-conclusion conduct of the parties. In particular, Article 31(3)(a) provides that, together with the context, one must consider “any subsequent agreement between the parties regarding the interpretation of the treaty or the application of its

²⁸ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (adopted 23 May 1969, entered into force 27 January 1980) 1155 UNTS 331.

²⁹ See Subsequent Agreement on the Interpretation of the Energy Charter Treaty (n 26) Preamble.

³⁰ Tibisay Morgandi and Lorand Bartels, ‘Exiting the Energy Charter Treaty under the Law of Treaties’ (2023) 34 *King's Law Journal* 145.

³¹ Subsequent Agreement on the Interpretation of the Energy Charter Treaty (n 26) Art. 2-3.

³² *Eskosol S.p.A. in liquidazione v Italian Republic* (ICSID Case No ARB/15/50) Award (4 September 2020) para 220.

provisions.”³³ This provision recognises that a treaty is not static; over time, parties may develop a mutual understanding or consistent practice that refines how the treaty’s terms are to be applied.³⁴

A subsequent agreement under Article 31(3)(a) is essentially an authentic interpretation, which is an agreement by all the parties, after the treaty’s conclusion, confirming how they interpret the treaty’s terms.³⁵ Crucially, however, the VCLT sets a high bar: to count as an authentic interpretation under Article 31(3)(a), the subsequent agreement or practice must reflect a consensus of all treaty parties.³⁶ This requirement is both procedural and substantive. Procedurally, it ensures that no subset of parties can impose an interpretation on others without their participation. Substantively, it preserves the reciprocity and balance of the treaty: one party cannot unilaterally reinterpret away an obligation to the detriment of another. In effect, Article 31(3)(a) guards against unilateral alterations of the treaty’s meaning masquerading as interpretations.³⁷ It codifies the common-sense notion that all parties to a treaty are masters of its meaning: just as their collective consent created the treaty, so any authoritative clarification of that treaty’s meaning requires collective endorsement.³⁸

In January 2019, shortly after *Achmea*, EU member states and the European Commission issued political declarations attempting to disavow intra-EU investor arbitration under various treaties.³⁹ This attempt, however, could not give the effect that EU states wanted.⁴⁰ A striking example is *Eskosol v. Italy*,⁴¹ where the tribunal faced the argument that the European Commission-led declaration should be treated as a binding interpretation of the ECT’s intra-EU scope. The *Eskosol* tribunal flatly rejected this, underscoring that Article 31(3)(a) requires agreement among all

³³ VCLT (n 28) Art. 31(3)(a).

³⁴ For more information and opposite views see: Ulf Linderfalk, ‘Doing the right thing for the right reason – why dynamic or static approaches should be taken in the interpretation of treaties’ (2008) 10 *International Community Law Review* 109.

³⁵ Luigi Crema, ‘Subsequent Agreements and Subsequent Practice within and Outside the Vienna Convention’ in Georg Nolte (ed), *Treaties and Subsequent Practice* (OUP 2013).

³⁶ *Eskosol v Italy* (n 32) para 220.

³⁷ Linderfalk (n 34).

³⁸ *Ibid.*

³⁹ European Commission (DG FISMA), ‘Declaration of the Member States of 15 January 2019 on the legal consequences of the *Achmea* judgment and on investment protection’.

⁴⁰ See *Vattenfall AB and Others v Germany* (ICSID Case No ARB/12/12) Award, 11 March 2021; *ESPF Beteiligungs GmbH and Others v Italy* (ICSID Case No ARB/16/5) Award, 14 September 2020.

⁴¹ *Eskosol v Italy* (n 32) para 220.

Contracting Parties, and that unilateral or plurilateral statements cannot rewrite a multilateral treaty by re-labeling themselves subsequent agreements.⁴²

Likewise, the Hungarian government openly broke ranks. Hungary refused to endorse the agreement that the ECT never applied intra-EU, explicitly noting that any such change requires unanimous consent.⁴³ Hungary's objection highlights that even within the EU, unanimity was lacking. Without the assent of all 50+ ECT contracting states, the EU's interpretative venture cannot qualify as a subsequent agreement under VCLT Article 31(3)(a). In short, the VCLT's unanimity rule blocks this attempt to achieve a binding interpretation through partial consent.

The tension in the EU's logic becomes even more apparent when considering the ECT's negotiating history (*travaux préparatoires*). Far from indicating an original intent to exclude intra-EU arbitration, the historical record suggests the opposite. During the 1990s ECT negotiations, the European Commission considered inserting a "disconnection clause,"⁴⁴ but ultimately no such clause was included.⁴⁵ The omission was deliberate; it reflected a choice that the ECT's obligations would apply fully between EU member states. Subsequent practice for decades reinforced this understanding: numerous intra-EU arbitrations proceeded under the ECT,⁴⁶ often with the European Commission participating as *amicus curiae* rather than asserting that the tribunal lacked jurisdiction *ab initio*. In fact, EU institutions repeatedly acknowledged that any intra-EU issue was a matter to be resolved internally or via treaty amendment, not by denying the applicability of the ECT itself. Thus, the EU's new narrative is historically untenable.

As the Swiss Supreme Court observed in 2022, it would violate *pacta sunt servanda* and basic good faith for a subgroup of states to unilaterally reinterpret a multilateral treaty in a way that

⁴² Ibid [222].

⁴³ Government of Hungary, 'Declaration of the Representative of the Government of Hungary, of 26 June 2024 on the legal consequences of the judgment of the Court of Justice in Komstroy and of the non-applicability of Article 26 of the Energy Charter Treaty as a basis for intra-EU arbitration proceedings' (June 2024).

⁴⁴ A standard device to exclude intra-bloc application of a multilateral treaty, as seen in some Council of Europe conventions, *see* Convention on Mutual Administrative Assistance in Tax Matters (opened for signature 25 January 1988, entered into force 1 April 1995) ETS No 127, Art. 27(2).

⁴⁵ European Energy Charter Conference Secretariat, 'Draft Basic Agreement for the European Energy Charter' (12 August 1992) 84, item 27.18; 'Draft Ministerial Declaration to the Energy Charter Treaty, Versions 2–7' (17 March 1994, Version 7) 6.

⁴⁶ For instance, *see Charanne BV and Construction Investments Sàrl v Kingdom of Spain* (SCC Case No V 062/2012) Award (21 January 2016) para 49.

nullifies obligations *inter se* that clearly existed on paper.⁴⁷ The Swiss Court pointed out that ECT signatories gave unconditional consent to arbitration in Article 26 ECT, and it refused to be swayed by the CJEU’s contrary reading, noting that Switzerland⁴⁸ never agreed to such an intra-EU carve-out.⁴⁹ This illustrates a broader principle: treaty terms must be interpreted consistently for all parties unless and until the treaty is actually amended. Allowing one region’s courts or a subset of states to declare a provision meaning “X for us, but Y for you” undermines the uniform application of the treaty and breaches the expectation of good faith performance owed to all other parties.

Finally, the EU agreement’s reliance on an *a fortiori* argument⁵⁰ blurs the line between interpretation and amendment to the point of doctrinal incoherence. The EU suggests that because *inter se* modifications are sometimes allowed under Article 41 VCLT, an interpretative accord among some parties should be even more permissible. This flips the hierarchy of treaty law. In reality, the VCLT drafters treated authentic interpretation as a higher bar precisely because it is retroactive and purports to bind everyone to a single understanding. If a mere subset of states could issue a binding “interpretation” with retroactive effect, more easily than they could amend the treaty prospectively, it would undermine Article 31’s stringent conditions and invite abuse: states could re-label modifications as “interpretations” to evade the need for broader consent. The *Eskosol*⁵¹ tribunal noted exactly this concern: the 2018 declaration by some EU states was “more in the nature of an attempted reservation to the ECT than a simple clarification.”⁵² Indeed, treaty interpretation cannot be used as a trojan horse to achieve what would otherwise require a formal amendment.

That said, article 31 and Article 41 VCLT govern fundamentally different juridical acts; conflating them is unwarranted. The EU’s intra-EU deal tries to straddle this line, but in doing so it finds little support in the law of treaties. Therefore, if the agreement has any legal viability, it must be found in the law of treaty modifications rather than interpretation. Having established that the VCLT’s

⁴⁷ *EDF Énergies Nouvelles SA v Kingdom of Spain* (Swiss Federal Supreme Court) 4A_244/2023 (3 April 2024).

⁴⁸ A non-EU party of the ECT.

⁴⁹ Swiss Supreme Court, 4A_244/2023, 3 April 2024 para 7.6.

⁵⁰ Subsequent Agreement on the Interpretation of the Energy Charter Treaty (n 26) Preamble.

⁵¹ *Eskosol v Italy* (n 32).

⁵² *Ibid* [225].

interpretation rules offer no shortcut for the EU's move, we turn now to the distinct question of treaty modification under international law.

2.2 Modifying a Multilateral Treaty Under Article 41 VCLT

Article 41 VCLT permits a subset of parties to a multilateral treaty to agree on modifications of the treaty among themselves, but it imposes three cumulative conditions for such an *inter se* arrangement to be lawful:

1. The modification must not be prohibited by the treaty.⁵³
2. The modification must not affect the enjoyment by other parties of their rights under the treaty, nor the performance of their obligations.⁵⁴
3. The modification must not relate to a provision derogation from which is incompatible with the effective execution of the treaty's object and purpose as a whole.⁵⁵

The EU's intra-EU agreement must satisfy all three conditions. We examine each in turn, in light of the ECT's terms and context.

2.2.1 Is the Modification Forbidden by the ECT?

The first question is whether the ECT itself prohibits the kind of *inter se* modification that the EU and its member states are attempting. The ECT does not contain an explicit clause banning *inter se* agreements, but it does include Article 16 that protects the treaty's key investor rights from being overridden by other agreements. It provides that if two or more contracting parties enter into a later international agreement concerning investment protection or dispute settlement, "*nothing in [the] other agreement shall be construed to derogate from any provision of Part III or V [of the ECT]... or from any right to dispute resolution with respect thereto under [the ECT].*"⁵⁶ In plain terms, Article 16 ensures that the ECT's substantive protections and dispute-resolution mechanism remain paramount if the same states have overlapping obligations under another treaty.

⁵³ VCLT (n 28) Art. 41(1)(b).

⁵⁴ VCLT (n 28) Art. 41(1)(b)(i).

⁵⁵ VCLT (n 28) Art. 41(1)(b)(ii).

⁵⁶ ECT (n 7) Art. 16.

Some might argue that Article 16 serves as an implicit barrier to the EU's strategy. The concern is that allowing a subgroup of parties to strip away investor protections among themselves would undermine the treaty's stability and purpose.⁵⁷ For example, in *Vattenfall v. Germany*,⁵⁸ the tribunal pointed to Article 16 and rejected the argument that EU law could nullify the ECT's arbitration clause in intra-EU relations.⁵⁹ It held that the *inter se* nullification implied by EU membership would be "prohibited by the [ECT], contrary to Article 41(1)(b) VCLT."⁶⁰ The tribunal reasoned that Article 16, as a *lex specialis*, expressly prevents EU member states from construing their EU-law obligations "so as to derogate from more favorable rights of the investor in Parts III and V ECT, including the right to dispute resolution."⁶¹ In other words, because intra-EU arbitration under the ECT is more favorable to investors than the absence of arbitration, Article 16 dictates that the ECT's arbitration clause must prevail over any conflicting *inter se* agreement or EU-law rule.⁶² The *Vattenfall* tribunal emphasised that Article 16 posed "an insurmountable obstacle" to the notion that EU member states could simply remove or ignore the ECT's protections among themselves.⁶³

Arbitral tribunals have offered subtly different takes on Article 16's effect. The tribunal in *Eskosol* observed that Article 16's "obvious object and purpose" is "to expand rather than curtail investor protections" in situations of overlapping treaties.⁶⁴ In the tribunal's view, when an investor has rights under both the ECT and another investment agreement, Article 16 logically allows the investor to choose which treaty's protections to invoke; it does not automatically nullify one forum or the other.⁶⁵ Under such a reading, an *inter se* agreement that purports to remove the ECT option would deprive investors of the very choice Article 16 intended to safeguard.

Crucially, no part of Article 16 explicitly mentions the "sunset clause." On its face, Article 16 speaks only to conflicts between the ECT and other agreements while the ECT is in force among

⁵⁷ Morgandi and Bartels (n 30).

⁵⁸ *Vattenfall v Germany* (n 40).

⁵⁹ *Ibid* [221].

⁶⁰ *Ibid*.

⁶¹ *Vattenfall AB and others v. Germany*, ICSID Case No. ARB/12/12, Decision on the *Achmea* Issue para 221.

⁶² *Eiser Infrastructure Ltd and Energia Solar Luxembourg Sàrl v Kingdom of Spain* (ICSID Case No ARB/13/36) Award, 4 May 2017 para 202.

⁶³ *Vattenfall v. Germany* (n 61) para 229.

⁶⁴ *Eskosol S.p.A. in liquidazione v Italy*, ICSID Case No ARB/15/50, Decision on Termination Request and Intra-EU Objection para 101.

⁶⁵ *Ibid*.

the parties; that said, it does not directly address post-withdrawal protection. This raises the question: does Article 16's shield extend to the sunset clause as well? A narrow reading might say no: the sunset clause is a distinct provision outside Parts III and V. However, treating the sunset clause's protections as wholly separate from the ECT's substantive guarantees would be artificial. The very purpose of a sunset clause is to extend the life of those investor rights⁶⁶ and the dispute mechanism⁶⁷ beyond withdrawal. In practice, the sunset clause is intertwined with investors' ability to enforce Part III and V rights; it is what allows an investor to invoke ECT arbitration even after a host state exits the treaty. Neutralising the sunset clause would effectively terminate investors' dispute-resolution rights years early, which is a clear reduction of protection. Given that the ECT, through Article 16, does not permit diminishing the dispute-resolution provision via a later agreement, the EU's manoeuvre is highly suspect under Article 16. In simple terms, if Article 16 means anything, it means that no subset of ECT parties can agree to offer investors less protection than the ECT provides. Yet the intra-EU agreement aims to do exactly that.

If Article 16 is indeed breached by the *inter se* agreement, the VCLT inquiry could end there: the modification would fail because it is "not permitted by the treaty." Even if one argues that Article 16 is not an absolute prohibition but merely a conflict rule, the practical outcome is the same: the ECT's more favorable terms are meant to prevail in any overlap. That means an *inter se* agreement which derogates from those terms would simply have no effect on an investor's ability to invoke the ECT in lieu of the less favorable agreement. In sum, Article 16 ECT is a significant legal obstacle for the EU agreement, one that the drafters of that agreement openly acknowledged.

2.2.2 Effect on Other Parties' Rights or Obligations

The second condition is that modification must not affect the rights of any parties outside the agreement. In other words, non-signatories to the *inter se* pact should continue to enjoy all their treaty rights, and their obligations should remain the same. Here, "party" means any state that is bound by the treaty and for which the treaty is in force.⁶⁸ Applying this to the ECT: any ECT

⁶⁶ ECT (n 7) Part III.

⁶⁷ ECT (n 7) Part V.

⁶⁸ VCLT (n 28) Art. 2(1)(g).

contracting party not joining the agreement should see no change in how the ECT operates with respect to them.

Therefore, as regards third states, the EU's modification is insulated. It is intended to function entirely within the EU's membership, essentially creating a self-contained regime for intra-EU relations. Non-EU contracting parties should experience the ECT exactly as before, with full rights to arbitration and treaty protection against EU states. In this sense, the second Article 41 requirement is met.

2.2.3 Consistency with the Treaty's Object and Purpose

The third and most nuanced condition is that an *inter se* modification must not be “incompatible with the effective execution of the object and purpose of the treaty as a whole”.⁶⁹ This criterion requires examining what the treaty's object and purpose actually are, and whether the proposed change undermines them.

Determining a treaty's “object and purpose” is an interpretative exercise, drawing on the treaty's text, preamble, annexes, and context, as well as any relevant extrinsic evidence.⁷⁰ The ECT's preamble emphasises the promotion of long-term cooperation in the energy field on the basis of complementarities and mutual benefits, the importance of energy security, and the efficient functioning of markets, while also taking into account environmental considerations.⁷¹ Article 2 of the ECT states: “This Treaty establishes a legal framework in order to promote long-term cooperation in the energy field, based on complementarities and mutual benefits, in accordance with the objectives and principles of the [Energy Charter].”⁷² The 1991 Energy Charter⁷³ elaborated these objectives, highlighting the need to create a favorable climate for investments⁷⁴

⁶⁹ VCLT (n 28) Article 41(1)(b)(ii).

⁷⁰ Oliver Dörr and Kirsten Schmalenbach (eds), *Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties: A Commentary* (2nd edn, Springer 2018) 560.

⁷¹ ECT (n 7) Title I, Preamble.

⁷² *Ibid* Art. 2.

⁷³ ‘European Energy Charter’ (The Hague, 17 December 1991).

⁷⁴ *Ibid* Title II, Section 4.

and the flow of technology, the importance of market principles in the energy sector, and commitments to environmental protection and energy efficiency.⁷⁵

From these sources, it is clear that the ECT was conceived with multiple aims. Investment protection is a central pillar.⁷⁶ At the same time, the ECT's object and purpose are not confined to investor rights.⁷⁷ The treaty also explicitly addresses energy security, market liberalisation, and environmental cooperation. Given these diverse objectives, assessing whether neutralising the sunset clause conflicts with the ECT's object and purpose can lead to two contrasting perspectives.

One could argue that protecting long-term energy investments is the keystone of the ECT's purpose, and that legal stability is essential for the treaty to fulfill its role. From this angle, the ECT's promise of protection was a fundamental part of the bargain that induced investments. Indeed, the inclusion of a 20-year sunset clause signals the parties' commitment to a stable, long-term framework. Under this view, stripping away the dispute resolution mechanism and cutting short the protection period guts a core objective of the treaty. The effective execution of the ECT's object and purpose would thus be impaired by an *inter se* modification that leaves a subset of the treaty covered by drastically different rules.

On the other hand, one might define the ECT's object and purpose in a more nuanced, multifaceted way that evolves over time.⁷⁸ Proponents of this view point out that the ECT is not solely an investors' charter; it also aims to facilitate sustainable energy cooperation, respect sovereignty, and even enhance environmental protection.⁷⁹ They might argue that the treaty's purpose can accommodate evolution. From this standpoint, the ECT's purpose of promoting "long-term cooperation in the energy field" might actually be served – not harmed – by freeing states to pursue decarbonisation policies without fear of ISDS claims. Moreover, the fact that the sunset clause was a later addition⁸⁰ suggests that it may not be part of the core object and purpose of the ECT, but

⁷⁵ Ibid Title I, Objectives.

⁷⁶ *Cem Cengiz Uzan v. Republic of Turkey* (SCC Case No. V 2014/023) Award on Respondent Bifurcated Preliminary Objection, 20 April 2016 para 152.

⁷⁷ Salma Mawa Kamila, 'Where is the Energy: Object and Purpose of the ECT under the Sunset Clause Scrutiny' (2024) 10(1) *Juris Gentium Law Review* 1.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Ibid.

⁸⁰ See European Energy Charter Conference Secretariat, 'Basic Agreement for the European Energy Charter' BA-4 (31 October 1991) Art. 44 (noting the EC and US proposal of a survival clause).

rather a supporting mechanism. Under this interpretation, removing the sunset clause *inter se* could be seen as a surgical tweak that does not strike at the heart of the treaty’s overall mission.

Both perspectives carry weight, and tribunals could adopt either when reviewing the EU’s agreement. The reality is that the ECT was designed to balance multiple objectives: encourage investment, ensure energy security, respect national sovereignty in energy policy, and promote sustainable development. Neutralising the sunset clause undoubtedly elevates some objectives at the expense of others. The key question is whether this re-balancing “impairs the effective execution” of the ECT’s overall purpose.⁸¹

How might we gauge impairment of a treaty’s purpose? The VCLT’s object-and-purpose test is generally understood as a high threshold – it would only catch modifications that strike at something essential to the treaty’s integrity.⁸² The commentary often distinguishes between treaties with reciprocal obligations and those with integral or absolute obligations.⁸³ The ECT, in structure, is largely a bundle of reciprocal promises. It does not establish an indivisible *erga omnes* regime like a humanitarian treaty would. That suggests *inter se* modifications might be viewed more permissibly.

However, arbitral tribunals have signaled that certain features of the ECT are so central that removing them even among some parties could contradict the treaty’s object and purpose. In *BayWa v. Spain*, the tribunal opined that “it is very doubtful” an *inter se* abrogation of the ECT among EU states is compatible with the treaty’s object and purpose.⁸⁴ It pointed specifically to Article 16 as evidence that preserving investor rights and access to arbitration is “a major plank of that multilateral treaty.”⁸⁵ In other words, if the ECT itself says “thou shalt not undermine these investor protections via other agreements,” that suggests those protections are integral to the

⁸¹ Kamila (n 77).

⁸² For example, core guarantees in a human rights treaty, or fundamental obligations in a disarmament treaty.

⁸³ Gerald Fitzmaurice, ‘Third report on the law of treaties’ (1958) *Yearbook of the International Law Commission* vol II 20, 27 (UN Doc A/CN.4/115), draft art 18(2).

⁸⁴ *BayWa r.e. Renewable Energy GmbH and BayWa r.e. Asset Holding GmbH v Kingdom of Spain* (ICSID Case No ARB/15/16) Decision on Jurisdiction, Liability and Directions on Quantum (2 December 2019) para 276.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.*

treaty's purpose. Other tribunals have noted that removing dispute settlement would undercut the ECT's aim of promoting investor confidence and FDI flows in the energy sector.⁸⁶

In any event, it is clear that the EU's *inter se* agreement sits in a grey zone with respect to Article 41(1)(b)(ii). On balance, the safer view is that the EU arrangement does conflict with the ECT's object and purpose, because it effectively excises the very provisions that give the treaty bite. In analogy, if a subset of parties to a trade agreement decided to eliminate *inter se* the dispute settlement and market access provisions, leaving only the preamble about cooperation, one could argue the treaty's purpose is frustrated among them.

Lastly, it is noteworthy that the ECT explicitly forbids reservations to any of its provisions.⁸⁷ It shows that when the treaty was drafted, the parties wanted a uniform, all-or-nothing acceptance. The Energy Charter Secretariat has likened the *inter se* agreement to a kind of post hoc "collective reservation," which they argue is exactly what the no-reservation clause was meant to prevent.⁸⁸ While the formal contexts differ,⁸⁹ the spirit is analogous: a group of parties is partially opting out of key obligations. That suggests the modification may indeed go to the core of the treaty's balance.

In conclusion, the object-and-purpose test under Article 41 VCLT poses perhaps the thorniest challenge for the EU's *inter se* pact. The ECT's objectives include providing a stable investment framework; removing the treaty's enforcement mechanism and cutting short protections for existing investments among EU states arguably eviscerates those aims in the very region that generated the majority of ECT cases. On the other hand, EU lawmakers justify the move as aligning the treaty with evolving climate and legal objectives, reflecting the fact that a 1990s fossil-focused pact has become an anachronism in the 2020s.⁹⁰ Ultimately, whether the modification is "compatible" with the ECT's purpose is a matter of interpretation – one likely to be tested in arbitration. At best, the EU's position will require tribunals to accept a dynamic reading of the

⁸⁶ *Vattenfall v Germany* (n 61) para 198.

⁸⁷ ECT (n 7) Art. 46.

⁸⁸ ECT Secretariat, 'Letter to the House of Representatives of Belgium' (23 February 2023).

⁸⁹ Article 19 VCLT explicitly states that a reservation may be formulated 'when signing, ratifying, accepting, approving or acceding to a treaty.' 'Consequently, reservations may not be made at a later stage.' See Council of Europe, Committee of Legal Advisers on Public International Law (CAHDI), 'Practical issues regarding reservations to international treaties' (*n.d.*).

⁹⁰ European Commission (DG Energy), 'European Commission proposes a coordinated EU withdrawal from the Energy Charter Treaty' (*News announcement*, 7 July 2023).

ECT's purpose, one that prioritises states' regulatory freedom and climate commitments over strict investment security. It is far from guaranteed that tribunals will share that view.

It bears mentioning that arbitral tribunals addressing these issues might not confine themselves to the VCLT. They could invoke broader principles to decide whether to honor or ignore the *inter se* agreement. Two concepts that loom large are "acquired rights" and "legitimate expectations." These are not explicitly mentioned in the VCLT, but they form part of the general international law context and could heavily influence an arbitral tribunal's stance. Essentially, even if the EU states ticked the VCLT's boxes, a tribunal might still ask: is it fundamentally fair or just to allow states to withdraw previously given rights from investors who relied on them? That question leads us into the next section, which examines how general international law principles might protect investors in the face of the EU's treaty alterations.

3. General International Law: Acquired Rights & Legitimate Expectations

Modern investment treaties occupy an unusual space in international law: they are contracts between states, but they confer benefits on non-state actors, namely investors.⁹¹ This hybrid nature has sparked debate on whether investors' treaty-based rights are merely derivative of the state-to-state agreement, or whether they attain a certain autonomy such that states cannot easily retract them once given.⁹² The EU's agreement to neutralise the ECT's sunset clause squarely raises this issue. Two related legal notions are often invoked in this context: acquired rights and legitimate expectations. While not codified in the ECT, these principles form part of the general law and have been recognised in arbitral jurisprudence.

3.1 Acquired Rights

The principle of acquired rights in international law holds that certain rights, once accrued to an individual or entity under an existing legal regime, should be respected and not easily taken away.⁹³

⁹¹ Campbell McLachlan, Laurence Shore and Matthew Weiniger, *International Investment Arbitration: Substantive Principles* (Oxford University Press 2007); Zachary Douglas, 'The Hybrid Foundation of Investment Treaty Arbitration' (2003) 74 *Brit YB Int'l L* 151, 181.

⁹² YiKang Zhang, 'Mutual Termination of Sunset Clauses in Intra-EU BITs: The Search for Investor Protections' (2018) 29(2) *The American Review of International Arbitration* 173.

⁹³ *Certain German Interests in Polish Upper Silesia (Germany v Poland)* (Merits) (Judgment, 25 May 1926) PCIJ Series A no 7, 42; *Questions relating to Settlers of German Origin in Poland* (Advisory Opinion, 10 September 1923)

In the context of investor–state relations, it is generally accepted that investments made and rights crystallised under a treaty are protected even if the legal framework later changes.⁹⁴ The contentious question here is whether the protection offered by a sunset clause itself can be considered an acquired right of the investor at the time of investment. In other words, when an investor invests in a host state while a treaty with a sunset clause is in force, does the investor thereby acquire a right to have the treaty’s protections continue for the additional period specified in that clause?

On one hand, it can be argued that a sunset clause is an integral part of the treaty’s “package” of guarantees.⁹⁵ By making an investment under a treaty that includes a 20-year sunset clause, the investor can claim to have acquired a right to the treaty’s continued application for that period, even if the treaty is later terminated or even if one party withdraws.⁹⁶ In this view, the sunset clause operates as a promise by the host state that treaty protections for existing investments will remain in place for the specified time, no matter what.

Several arbitral decisions support this perspective. For example, the tribunal in *Adria Group v. Croatia*⁹⁷ emphasised that investors who invested while a BIT was in force could not be retroactively deprived of the rights offered at that time.⁹⁸ The BIT’s offer of arbitration, once made and relied upon by an investor, could not suddenly be negated by the states’ later change of heart. The tribunal bluntly rejected the notion that investors were mere incidental beneficiaries of state agreements, calling that view “belong[ing] to an earlier era of international law in which States were considered to be the only ‘subjects’ of international law.”⁹⁹ In the tribunal’s words, the BIT

PCIJ Series B no 6, 40; see generally Pierre A Lalive, ‘The Doctrine of Acquired Rights’ in Southwestern Legal Foundation (ed), *Rights and Duties of Private Investors Abroad* (Matthew Bender 1965) 145.

⁹⁴ Malcolm N Shaw, *International Law* (9th edn, Cambridge University Press 2021) 870–71.

⁹⁵ Kőhegyi Dávid, ‘The Power of Sunset Clauses Put to the Test: Can Intra-EU BITs Be Back from the Dead?’ (*DLA Piper* 2024).

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*

⁹⁷ *Adria Group BV and Adria Group Holding BV v Republic of Croatia* (ICSID Case No ARB/20/6) Decision on Intra-EU Jurisdictional Objection (31 October 2023).

⁹⁸ *Ibid* [242].

⁹⁹ *Ibid* [240].

“conferred rights directly upon” investors,¹⁰⁰ and once those rights vested through an investment, they could not be withdrawn outside the treaty’s own terms.¹⁰¹

In *Magyar Farming v. Hungary*,¹⁰² the tribunal likewise underscored that the inclusion of a 20-year sunset clause in the BIT reflected the contracting states’ acknowledgment that the long-term interests of investors must be respected even upon termination.¹⁰³ The tribunal noted that even when states terminate a treaty by mutual consent, “they acknowledge that long-term interests of investors who have invested in the host State in reliance on the treaty guarantees must be respected. This is the purpose served by the 20-year sunset provision.”¹⁰⁴ In short, from this perspective, the sunset clause’s post-termination protection is a vested right that investors acquired at the moment of investing under the treaty.

On the other hand, one might argue that treaty guarantees are ultimately creatures of the state-to-state agreement and do not, by themselves, give investors an irrevocable property right in the treaty’s continuance.¹⁰⁵ From this perspective, investors benefit from the treaty’s protections only for as long as the treaty remains in force, unless the investor has taken concrete steps to “crystallise” a claim.¹⁰⁶ Thus, states retain the sovereign prerogative to modify or terminate their treaty obligations by mutual consent, even if doing so curtails benefits that investors previously enjoyed. Unless the treaty explicitly restricts the states’ ability to terminate or amend the sunset clause, investors cannot claim that such a clause is immune from change.¹⁰⁷

Proponents of this view argue that simply making an investment is not enough to “vest” treaty protections irrevocably in the investor for decades to come.¹⁰⁸ The investor and the host state do not have a contractual privity whereby one party’s acceptance permanently fixes the other’s

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Ibid [243].

¹⁰² *Magyar Farming Company Ltd, Kintyre Kft and Inicia Zrt v Hungary* (ICSID Case No ARB/17/27) Award (13 November 2019).

¹⁰³ Ibid [223].

¹⁰⁴ Ibid.

¹⁰⁵ Anthea Roberts, ‘Triangular treaties: the extent and limits of investment treaty rights’ (2015) 56 *Harvard International Law Journal* 353, 409.

¹⁰⁶ Johannes Tropper and August Reinisch, ‘The 2020 Termination Agreement of Intra-EU BITs and its effect on investment arbitration in the EU – a public international law analysis of the Termination Agreement’ (2022) 16 *Austrian Yearbook on International Arbitration* 301.

¹⁰⁷ Roberts (n 105).

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

obligations.¹⁰⁹ Rather, a treaty is an expression of the joint sovereign will of the state parties.¹¹⁰ As sovereigns, the states are entitled to change the treaty as they see fit, even if doing so revokes or modifies benefits previously extended.¹¹¹ Unless the treaty itself says that the sunset clause cannot be turned off by mutual agreement, the default is that the states, as “masters of the treaty,” can withdraw that benefit by the same consensual process by which they gave it.¹¹²

Comparing the treaty parties to a joint legislator would support this view: just as a state can generally change its domestic laws, two states can change their treaty by agreement despite investors’ reliance. An investor, therefore, cannot lock in favorable treaty provisions simply by accepting them, because the investor has no say in the treaty’s continuance and the treaty parties have not surrendered their power to alter their mutual obligations.¹¹³

In practice, if one accepts that sunset clauses do not create immutable individual rights, then the EU member states could jointly neutralise the ECT’s sunset clause via an *inter se* agreement without violating the principle of acquired rights. Conversely, if a sunset clause is deemed to confer a vested right upon investors at the time of investment, then neither one state’s unilateral withdrawal nor even a mutual *inter se* agreement can retroactively deprive investors of that additional protection period. Those investors would be entitled to invoke the clause and have the treaty remain applicable for their investments.

A parallel can be drawn to how some tribunals have treated other treaty clauses with an element of timing. Consider the ECT’s “denial of benefits” clause (Article 17), which allows a state to withdraw treaty benefits from certain investors if certain conditions are met.¹¹⁴ The ECT does not specify when this denial can be invoked. In *Plama Consortium v. Bulgaria*,¹¹⁵ the investor argued that Bulgaria could not invoke Article 17 after the dispute arose, because the investor had no warning and had already relied on the treaty. The tribunal agreed, holding that a state must exercise denial of benefits prospectively, not retroactively, otherwise an investor could be “lured” by the

¹⁰⁹ Aristides N Hatzis, ‘Rights and obligations of third parties’ in Boudewijn Bouckaert and Gerrit De Geest (eds), *Encyclopedia of Law and Economics*, vol III: The Regulation of Contracts (Edward Elgar 2000) 200, 210.

¹¹⁰ Lord McNair, *The Law of Treaties* (Clarendon Press 1961) 365.

¹¹¹ Roberts (n 105).

¹¹² *Ibid.*

¹¹³ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁴ See ECT (n 7) Art. 17.

¹¹⁵ *Plama Consortium Ltd v Bulgaria* (ICSID Case No ARB/03/24) Decision on Jurisdiction (8 February 2005).

treaty's protections only to have them yanked away later.¹¹⁶ It noted that if a state could wait until after a claim is filed to deny benefits, it would make a mockery of investors' legitimate reliance and the certainty of consent to arbitration.¹¹⁷ By analogy, one could argue that the mid-stream neutralisation of a sunset clause has a retroactive character – it takes away a protection that investors were promised at the time of investing. Such an action risks being seen as defeating investors' reasonable expectations, and thus contrary to principles of legal certainty and fairness ingrained in international law.

In sum, the concept of acquired rights provides a lens to question whether the EU's intra-EU agreement can validly extinguish investors' ability to invoke the ECT during what would have been the sunset period. There is support in arbitral jurisprudence for the notion that investors, having invested under the treaty, have a right to the treaty's promised protections for the life of the sunset clause. However, there is also authority for the proposition that states remain free to alter their treaty commitments by mutual consent, especially if they do so explicitly, as long as they are not targeting vested claims. The outcome likely will depend on tribunals' philosophical leanings: a more investor-centric view sees the treaty as *quasi-legislative* with direct rights that harden upon investment, whereas a more state-centric view sees the treaty as a contract that the parties can together rewrite or nullify, with investors' rights always conditioned on the treaty remaining in force.

Even if one stops short of saying the sunset clause itself is a “vested” right, investors can argue that they made their investments in reliance on the availability of that clause's protection. In other words, while the right to extended protection might not vest immediately upon investing, the investor legitimately counted on that safety net being there if needed. This line of reasoning shades into the doctrine of legitimate expectations, which we address next. The core idea is that investors structure long-term projects based on the legal assurances in place, including the treaty's dispute resolution mechanism and any sunset clause. To later remove those protections – especially retroactively – could be seen as undermining the expectations that guided the investment decision.

¹¹⁶ Ibid [162].

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

3.2 Legitimate Expectations

The doctrine of legitimate expectations is a cornerstone of the fair and equitable treatment (FET) standard found in most IIAs, including the ECT.¹¹⁸ In essence, it protects an investor's expectation that the host state will provide a stable, predictable legal and business environment,¹¹⁹ and that the rules of the game will not be arbitrarily changed after the investment is made.¹²⁰ One frequently cited definition comes from the *Tecmed v. Mexico* award,¹²¹ which stated that a foreign investor expects the host state to act "in a consistent manner, free from ambiguity and totally transparently in its relations with the foreign investor, so that it may know beforehand any and all rules and regulations that will govern its investments."¹²² While some tribunals have criticised this *Tecmed* formulation as overly broad,¹²³ the basic idea is widely accepted: if a state induces an investment by making certain assurances, it would be unfair to then pull the rug out from under the investor by renegeing on those assurances.¹²⁴

In the context of the ECT's withdrawal, investors might argue that the very inclusion of the 20-year sunset clause gave them a legitimate expectation that the treaty's protections would continue to shield their investments for that additional period. The sunset clause can be seen as an explicit promise of stability: a guarantee that the rules in place at the time of investment will not suddenly vanish if the treaty ends. From an investor's standpoint, this assurance was part of the package of rights that attracted them and guided their risk assessment. As one commentary observes, investment treaties are ultimately "reliance-inducing devices" – states offer guarantees specifically to encourage investors to commit capital, and investors reasonably rely on those guarantees when making investment decisions.¹²⁵ Under this view, the temporal scope of protection is as much a part of the bargain as the substantive standards themselves. International law, so the argument

¹¹⁸ ECT (n 7) Art. 10.

¹¹⁹ *Técnicas Medioambientales Tecmed SA v The United Mexican States* (ICSID Case No ARB(AF)/00/2) Award (29 May 2003) para 154.

¹²⁰ *International Thunderbird Gaming Corporation v The United Mexican States* (UNCITRAL) Award (26 January 2006) para 147.

¹²¹ *Tecmed v The United Mexican States* (n 119).

¹²² *Ibid* [154].

¹²³ For instance, see *White Industries Australia Limited v. The Republic of India* (UNCITRAL) Award (30 November 2011) para 10.3.6.

¹²⁴ Aceris Law LLC, 'Legitimate expectations in investment arbitration' (*Aceris Law*, 14 October 2018).

¹²⁵ Barbara Łyszczarz, 'Treaty Terminating the Intra-EU BITs: a Game-Changer or ... Not?' (*American Review of International Arbitration (ARIA)*, 22 September 2020).

goes, should uphold the investor's legitimate reliance not only on the treaty's substantive and procedural provisions, but also on "their lifespan determined by the sunset clauses."¹²⁶

However, asserting a legitimate expectation based on a treaty provision faces several challenges. First, there is the principle of state sovereignty and the recognised right of states to modify or terminate treaties by mutual consent, especially for *bona fide* public policy reasons.¹²⁷ International law generally permits states to renegotiate their obligations; an investor cannot expect a host state to freeze its international commitments in perpetuity, particularly commitments that are reciprocal between states.¹²⁸

Second, tribunals have consistently held that an investor's expectations are only protected if they are reasonable and legitimate in light of the circumstances, and typically if they are based on specific assurances made by the state to the investor.¹²⁹ A general legislative or treaty provision applicable to all investors is sometimes deemed too broad or not specific enough to form the basis of a concrete legitimate expectation, absent evidence that the investor personally relied on it.¹³⁰ For instance, if a state changes its regulations in a way that negatively affects an investment, that alone is not a breach of FET unless the investor can point to a particular promise or the overall stability of the framework at the time of investment. In the context of treaties, an expectation that the treaty will remain in force forever may not be reasonable. The question is whether expecting the sunset clause to be honored is more like expecting a law not to change or expecting a promise made to you to be kept. It could be argued either way.

One key factor is timing and knowledge. By the late 2010s, any investor paying attention would know that intra-EU investment arbitration was under siege. The 2018 *Achmea* judgment put investors on notice that intra-EU BIT arbitration clauses were considered invalid by the EU's highest court.¹³¹ In January 2019, the EU member states themselves, in their political declarations,

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ *Commission v Koninklijke Friesland Campina NV* (C-519/07 P) [2009] ECR I-8495, [2010] 1 CMLR 13, para 85.

¹²⁸ Emmanuel T Laryea, 'Legitimate expectations in investment treaty law: concept and scope of application' in Julien Chaisse, Leïla Choukroune and Sufian Jusoh (eds), *Handbook of International Investment Law and Policy* (Springer Singapore 2021) 97.

¹²⁹ For example, see *EDF (Services) Ltd v Romania* (ICSID Case No ARB/05/13) Award (8 October 2009) para 217.

¹³⁰ Laryea (n 128).

¹³¹ Sabina Kubsik, 'Consequences of the Achmea judgement for intra-EU arbitrations based on the Energy Charter Treaty' (*Lexology*, 3 December 2020).

announced their intention to terminate intra-EU BITs.¹³² In May 2020, most of those states signed the termination treaty, explicitly abolishing all intra-EU BITs and their sunset clauses.¹³³ When *Komstroy* came in 2021, it foreshadowed the end of intra-EU ECT arbitration as well.¹³⁴ Finally, through 2022–2023, one EU state after another declared it would exit the ECT, and the European Commission openly developed the *inter se* neutralisation plan. All of this was public. Thus, an investor who invested after these developments might have a hard time claiming a legitimate expectation that ECT protection would remain available. As the tribunal in *Saluka v. Czech Republic*¹³⁵ noted, no investor may reasonably expect the laws to remain completely unchanged over decades, especially against a backdrop of shifting public policies¹³⁶ – investors must anticipate that the regulatory or legal environment can evolve, and their expectations must adapt accordingly.

In Scanlon’s theoretical terms, a promise or assurance creates an obligation if one party intentionally induces a certain expectation in another, and the latter relies on it.¹³⁷ Applying this to our case: when the EU states offered the ECT’s protections to investors in the 1990s, they intentionally held out an assurance of stability because they wanted investors to rely on it. Many investors did rely. Now, decades later, the states seek to withdraw that assurance for the sake of other goals. Is there a “special justification,” to use Scanlon’s phrasing, that excuses breaking the earlier assurance?¹³⁸ The EU would argue yes: the imperative of upholding EU law and the exigencies of climate change policy justify the move. Moreover, some could argue that the assurance was implicitly conditional – the possibility of a treaty or its clauses termination exists in international law, and sophisticated investors know treaties are not eternal.

¹³² Johannes Tropper, ‘The treaty to end all investment treaties: The Termination Agreement of intra-EU BITs and its effect on sunset clauses’ (*Völkerrechtsblog*, 12 May 2020).

¹³³ *Agreement for the termination of Bilateral Investment Treaties between the Member States of the European Union* [2020] OJ L 169/1.

¹³⁴ Kartik Sharma, ‘The Conundrum of the Komstroy Declaration: A Case of Interpreting or Modifying the Energy Charter Treaty?’ (*Völkerrechtsblog*, 27 November 2024).

¹³⁵ *Saluka Investments BV v Czech Republic* (UNCITRAL) Partial Award (17 March 2006).

¹³⁶ *Ibid* [305].

¹³⁷ TM Scanlon, *What We Owe to Each Other* (Belknap Press 1998) 304, cited in Teerawat Wongkaew, *Protection of Legitimate Expectations in Investment Treaty Arbitration: A Theory of Detrimental Reliance* (Cambridge University Press 2019) 62.

¹³⁸ *Ibid*.

What about the climate policy justification? The EU often frames the ECT exit as necessary to remove protections for fossil fuels. However, as noted *supra*, many ECT arbitration claims have been brought by renewable energy investors against states for cutting renewable subsidies – so the treaty has protected green investments too.¹³⁹ In fact, one could argue that by terminating intra-EU ECT protection, the EU is also removing protections from renewable energy investors who might need them. This undercuts the narrative that it's solely about fossil fuels.

In the final analysis, the principle of legitimate expectations underscores the importance of fairness and reliance. If a tribunal were sympathetic to investors, it might rule that applying the *inter se* agreement to an investment made before all these withdrawal signals would violate FET – essentially a breach by the state of the investor's legitimate expectation that the ECT would be available for the promised period. That could give rise to liability, even as the treaty is being dismantled. On the other hand, a tribunal more deferential to state prerogatives could find that the investor's expectation was not legitimate in the face of compelling reasons of public policy and the general revocability of treaties.

In sum, while legitimate expectations is not a magic bullet guaranteeing treaty stability, it is a lens through which tribunals will likely view the EU's actions. It adds a layer of equitable considerations: even if legally the states can do what they did, was it fair to investors who counted on a different outcome? The answer may depend on specific facts, timing, and the tribunal's temperament. It is entirely possible that we will see divergent outcomes in different cases: some arbitrators might accept the EU's intra-EU agreement as a lawful exercise of state authority, while others might effectively nullify it in practice by holding states to their prior promises where investors reasonably relied on them.

4. Conclusion

The EU's bid to neutralise the ECT's sunset clause through an *inter se* arrangement exemplifies an ambitious yet legally fraught exercise. By coordinating a withdrawal from the ECT and simultaneously invoking a subsequent agreement among themselves, the EU and its member states

¹³⁹ Peter Cameron, 'New types of energy disputes' in Cavinder Bull, Loretta Malintoppi and Constantine Partasides (eds), *Arbitration's Age of Enlightenment?* (Kluwer Law International 2023) 737-747.

seek to reinterpret or modify the treaty's application so that its 20-year sunset period will not operate in intra-EU relations. This approach rests on twin pillars of treaty law: VCLT Article 31(3)(a), which in theory allows parties to agree on a treaty's interpretation, and VCLT Article 41, which permits *inter se* modifications in limited circumstances. Both pillars, however, stand on uncertain ground in this case.

The use of Article 31(3)(a) blurs the line between interpretation and amendment. An authentic joint interpretation requires unanimity. What the EU calls an interpretation looks to others like a unilateral rewrite, raising the fundamental objection that one cannot interpret a multilateral treaty *inter se* to mean it never meant what it plainly said.¹⁴⁰ Meanwhile, Article 41 VCLT does contemplate modifications among some parties, but under strict conditions that aim to protect both the treaty's integrity and third-party interests. Whether the EU's agreement meets those conditions is debatable. Article 16 ECT, the treaty's non-derogation clause, appears to explicitly guard against exactly this kind of diminishment of investor protections. Even beyond Article 16, one can argue that removing the key dispute-settlement and investment guarantees among a large subset of ECT parties is "incompatible with the effective execution of [the treaty's] object and purpose."¹⁴¹ After all, the ECT was fundamentally about providing a reliable investment regime in the energy sector; excising its enforcement mechanism and cutting short protections undercuts that reliability. Arbitral tribunals have indeed hinted that such an *inter se* move would violate the treaty's spirit and architecture. These legal ambiguities underscore that the EU's manoeuvre, while innovative, sits at the edge of what international treaty law permits.

Compounding these treaty-law questions are the unresolved issues of investors' rights under general international law. Investment treaties like the ECT straddle contract and legislation. Do investors have a direct right to the promised 20-year protection, such that taking it away would offend principles of acquired rights or legitimate expectations? There is no definitive answer yet. Some tribunals, as we have seen, view investors' treaty rights as having a life of their own once investments are made. By that logic, the EU states' attempt to extinguish those rights among themselves could be deemed ineffective or even wrongful *vis-à-vis* investors. Other tribunals might

¹⁴⁰ Richard K Gardiner, *Treaty Interpretation* (2nd ed., Oxford University Press 2015) 250.

¹⁴¹ VCLT (n 28) Art. 41(1)(b)(ii).

emphasise the states' sovereignty and the fact that investors are ultimately third-party beneficiaries who cannot veto states' mutual decisions to alter a treaty.

This tension lies at the heart of the matter. The EU's approach tests how far international law will accommodate collective action to repudiate investor-state arbitration, a mechanism increasingly viewed by some governments as overreaching. If successful, the intra-EU agreement could become a template for like-minded states to cooperatively unwind investment treaties that have outlived their political acceptance.¹⁴² If it fails, it will reinforce the durability of treaty commitments and potentially oblige the EU states to endure the sunset period or negotiate a broader multilateral solution.

As of this writing, the outcome remains uncertain.¹⁴³ What is clear is that the EU's strategy, born of genuine policy concerns, inhabits a legal grey zone. It is neither clearly sanctioned nor clearly forbidden by existing rules. The ultimate verdict on its legality will likely come through arbitral decisions or perhaps national court judgments in enforcement proceedings. Those decisions will have ramifications far beyond the ECT, as they will signal how international law balances treaty flexibility with stability in the investment regime.

In closing, the EU's innovative path to disarm the ECT's sunset clause highlights both the adaptability and the fragility of the international legal order. It demonstrates that states, when confronted with normative conflicts, will seek creative solutions. Yet it also shows that such creativity has limits: treaties are founded on consent and good faith, and workarounds that strain those foundations risk undermining trust in international commitments. The energy transition and climate imperatives might well necessitate unprecedented legal adjustments. However, ideally, these should be achieved in a way that maintains respect for the rule of law and the legitimate

¹⁴² As of this writing, there is one call. The European Economic and Social Committee urged the EU to strike an *inter se* agreement with non-EU parties to neutralise the ECT's sunset clause. See European Economic and Social Committee, 'Decision on the interpretation and application of the Energy Charter Treaty' (Opinion REX/593-EESC-2024, 4 December 2024).

¹⁴³ Two ICSID tribunals—*Saptec, S.A. v Kingdom of Spain* (ICSID Case No ARB/19/23) and *European Solar Farms A/S v Kingdom of Spain* (ICSID Case No ARB/18/45)—are reported to have declined jurisdiction; this was stated in a press release by Spain's Ministry for the Ecological Transition, and, as of this writing, the awards are not publicly available and the outcome remains uncertain. See Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 'España gana dos laudos de energías renovables por falta de jurisdicción de los tribunales arbitrales' (Press release, 14 October 2024).

interests of all stakeholders. The EU's experience with the ECT will be an instructive case study in whether that balance can be struck.